

AN ALTERNATIVE METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

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ABSTRACT

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There are many kinds of equations based on the elementary beam theory to calculate the energy release rate for the double cantilever beam. Essentially, they are the same and can be easily transferred to the interested one by using the load-displacement relation at the beam tip. However, it is found that the accuracy of these equations in calculating the energy release rate is different. The equation (11) which does not include the crack length is within 0.5% of accuracy compared to the finite element analysis result even for short crack. While, there is a remarkable error in the alternative equation in the calculation of the energy release rate, especially for short crack. Based on equation (11), a procedure for measuring the interlaminar fracture toughness is proposed. Three different thicknesses of DCBs are used to apply and verify the proposed method, very good agreements of the results from the present method and the ASTM standard methods are observed. The present method is simple to conduct compared to the ASTM standard methods, where tedious measurements of the growing crack length are required.

1. Introduction:

Due to the low strengths of the composite material in the thickness direction, delamination is one of the most serious failure modes in composite materials and structures [1-2]. Therefore, the measurement of the interlaminar fracture toughness is extremely important in the design and analysis of composite materials and structures. A various test specimens are designed to obtain the interlaminar fracture toughness. Among the specimens, the double cantilever beam is widely used and adopted in the ASTM standard. The effects of the insert thickness, load type and rate on the measured interlaminar fracture toughness are studied. The standard suggests using non-adhesive insert e.g. PEFA film as crack initiator and yields consistent results [3]. In addition, the influence of the specimen thickness [4-6], width [4] and crack length on the critical energy rate G_{IC} in thermosetting [7] and thermoplastic composites [8] were studied to see the critical energy rate is a material property or geometry dependent as well.

For most of carbon fiber reinforced composites, they are treated as linear elasticity. Delamination is regarded as crack propagation. Thus, linear elastic fracture mechanics is widely used in the delamination analysis of composite materials and many methods were proposed to calculate the fracture toughness [9-11]. The most straightforward method is the work –area method, which is directly based on the definition of the energy release rate. To obtain the work area under the load-displacement curve, periodical unloading and reloading procedure was required. However, the accuracy of the fracture

toughness obtained from this tedious procedure was not satisfied, when compared to the alternative methods recommended by the ASTM standard [3]. Three data reduction methods are recommended by ASTM standard [3], which are modified beam theory (MBT), Berry's compliance calibration (CC) [10] method and modified compliance calibration (MCC) method, respectively. All of these three methods require the measurement of the applied load and its associated displacement and crack length to obtain the relation between the compliance and crack length. In fact, it is not easy to measure the growing crack length and to record the corresponding load and displacement simultaneously. Therefore, uncertainty is introduced in the MBT, CC and MCC methods [11].

From the material testing and characterization point of view, it is highly desirable to have a testing procedure which is easy to prepare, conduct and yields consistent results. To meet this demand, a simple method for measuring the interlaminar fracture toughness of composites by using the DCB specimen is proposed in this paper.

2. Evaluation of the equations to the energy release rate for the DCB

2.1 Energy release rate G

Energy release rate is the energy lost per unit of newly created surface area in fracture process. Based on fracture mechanics, it means the energy supplied to crack tip for it to grow must be balanced by the amount of the energy that lost because of the formation of new surfaces. In the mathematical form, it can be expressed as follows:

$$G = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial A} = \frac{\partial (W - U)}{\partial A} = \frac{1}{2B} \frac{\partial (W - U)}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where, U represents the total strain energy, W is the potential work from any external forces, and A refers to the newly created surface area.

For fixed displacement loading condition, $\delta u = 0$, $\delta W = 0$, therefore,

$$G = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial A} = \frac{\partial (W - U)}{\partial A} = -\frac{1}{2B} \cdot \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Energy release rate based on the beam theory for DCB

For the double cantilever beam, an approximate approach to obtain the energy release rate is by using the elementary beam theory, where the external potential work and strain energy can be obtained in closed-form. According to the Euler beam theory, the relationship between the displacement δ and load P at the tip of a single arm is,

$$\delta = \frac{Pa^3}{3E_{11}I} \quad (3)$$

Where, E_{11} is the Young's modulus along the fiber direction, a represents the length of the beam, I is the cross section inertia moment.

The deformation induced by the shear force is not considered in the Euler expression. If the deformation is involved, the following expression for δ and P can be obtained from Timoshenko beam theory:

$$\delta = \frac{Pa^3}{3E_{11}I} + \frac{Pa}{AG_{13}k} \quad (4)$$

Where, k is the shear stress correction factor, which is 5/6 for an isotropic rectangular cross-section

beam, G_{13} is the shear modulus and A is the cross section area of each beam. The second term on right of Eq.(5) is the deformation due to the shear force.

The total strain energy stored in the beam is:

$$U = 1/2 \cdot P\delta \quad (5)$$

Using the fixed displacement loading condition and Eqs. (2, 3, and 5), the energy release rate can be expressed as:

$$G = - \frac{1}{B} \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \Big|_{\delta} = \frac{9EI \cdot \delta^2}{2B \cdot a^4} \quad (6)$$

Using Eq.(3), the energy release rate G in Eq.(6) can be rewritten as following,

$$G = \frac{3P\delta}{2Ba} \quad (7)$$

$$G = \frac{1}{2B} \cdot \frac{P^2 a^2}{E_{11} I} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, using the load-displacement relation based on the Timoshenko beam theory, the energy release rate G is:

$$G = \frac{1}{2B} \cdot \frac{P^2 a^2}{E_{11} I} + \frac{3P^2}{2B \cdot AG_{13} k} \quad (9)$$

With the measured crack length a , the corresponding load and displacement at the beam tip, the fracture toughness can be obtained by using Eq. (7). For Eqs. (8-9), the displacement is not required, while the measured crack length is needed. Sun and Zheng [12] had pointed out that in the DCB tests, the crack front is like a thumb nail which means the crack length, a , at the specimen edge is smaller than that in the middle. In addition, there are some uncertainties introduced in the measurement of a growing crack length and its associated load and displacement. Therefore, the equations required the crack length a may be not accurate for measuring the critical energy release rate G . However, using Eq. (3), the crack length of the DCB can be given by,

$$a = \sqrt[3]{3E_{11} I \delta / P} \quad (10)$$

Substitution Eq.(10) into Eq. (7) leads to:

$$G = \frac{(3E_{11} I \delta)^{2/3} P^{4/3}}{BE_{11} I} \quad (11)$$

This equation is named as LD relation in this paper. The crack length is not needed in calculating the energy release rate.

2.4 FEM validation

It is noteworthy that some approximations are introduced in the beam model in calculating the energy release rate G . For examples, the boundary condition at the beam tip is fixed in the calculation of the energy release rate and the strain energy is only stored in the arms. In fact, there is some rotation at the

end of the crack tip. In addition, the strain energy at the crack tip cannot be ignored. Therefore, the equations for calculating the energy release rate G based on the solution from the beam may not be accurate enough. A two-dimensional finite element mode is used to verify the accuracy of Eqs. (8-9) in calculating G . The geometry of the DCB is shown in Fig.1, where a concentration force is applied at the location of the top hinge. The moment in the x and y directions of the node at the bottom hinge is fixed. Both unidirectional carbon fiber composite and isotropic aluminum are used in the finite element modes. The properties of the composite are given in Table.1.

Figure 1: Boundary conditions of the FEM model

The finite element mode for the DCB is shown in Fig.2. The one quarter noded singular element around the crack tip is used to model the singularity of the crack tip. The other regions are modeled by quadratic plane stress element CPS8R. The J -integral method implemented in ABAQUS is used to obtain the energy release rate. For unidirectional carbon fiber composite, the energy release rates obtained from the finite element are shown in Fig.3 (a). Also shown in this figure are the results determined by using beam theory in Eqs. (8-9). The relative difference between the energy release rate obtained from Eqs. (8-9) and the finite element analysis are given Fig.3 (b). Similarly, the energy release rate and the relative difference are shown in Fig.4 (a) and Fig.4 (b), respectively, for isotropic DCB. It is also worth to note that all the equations given in Eqs. (8-9) are derived from the beam theory. However, the accuracy of these equations are quite different as shown in Fig.3 (b) and Fig.4 (b). It is observed that the energy release rate obtained from Eq.(11) is the most accurate for both composite and aluminum, compared to the results obtained from FEM. Therefore, Eq. (11) can be directly used for the determination of the interlaminar fracture toughness.

Figure 2: Finite element model for the DCB

Mechanical constants(Units)	Magnitude
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1 (GPa)	110.00
Transverse Young's modulus, E_2, E_3 (GPa)	8.066
Shear moduli, G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	3.790
Shear moduli, G_{23} (GPa)	3.280
Poisson's ratios, ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.321
Poisson's ratios, ν_{23}	0.45

Table 1: Mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon fiber composite

Figure 3: a) Energy release rates for a various a/h for unidirectional carbon fiber composite, and b) Relative difference between the energy release rate obtained from Eqs. (8-9) and FEM

Figure 4: a) Energy release rates isotropic aluminum. b) Relative difference between the energy release rate obtained from Eqs. (8-9) and FEM

3. Data reduction methods for determining the fracture toughness

It is found from section 2.4 that Eq.(11) is accurate for calculating the energy release rate. A method based on Eq. (11) is proposed to measure the fracture toughness. In addition, the MBT, CC and MCC methods used in the ASTM standard are introduced for comparison purpose.

3.1 MBT

As shown in section 2, there are some approximation introduced in the beam model for calculating the energy release rate. In addition, the crack length is not uniform across the width of DCB and it the fracture toughness is overestimated by using Eq. (7). To correct this and consider the rotation of the

beam the tip, an equivalent crack length is proposed by Williams [13] as follows.

$$a_{eq} = (a + |\Delta|) \quad (12)$$

Therefore, the fracture toughness is,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2B(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (13)$$

where, Δ is determined by generating a least squares plot of the cube root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$, as a function of crack length according to ASTM Standard D5528.

3.2 CC

In this method, a least squares plot of $\log(\delta_i/P_i)$ versus $\log(a_i)$ is generated by using the visually observed crack length and its associate load displacement. A linear relation is used to fit these data. The slop of this line is n . And the Mode I fracture toughness is calculated by,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{nP\delta}{2Ba} \quad (14)$$

3.3 MCC

MCC is the Modified Compliance Calibration method whose equation can be expressed as:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P^2C^{2/3}}{2A_1Bh} \quad (15)$$

In this method, a least squares plot of the ratio of crack length and thickness, a/h , as a function of the cube root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$, is plotted. The coefficient A_1 in Eq.(15) is the slop of this line.

3.4 LD (load-displacement) method

As shown in Section 2.4, Eq. (11) is accurate for calculating the energy release rate. The load and displacement required in the Eq. (11) are accessible from the load cell of the test machine. To use Eq. (11), an additional tensile test is needed to obtain the Young's module of the beam. Once the modulus is determined, the interlaminar fracture toughness can be calculated with the load-displacement relation from the DCB tests by,

$$G = \frac{(3E_{11}I\delta)^{2/3}P^{4/3}}{BE_{11}I} \quad (16)$$

4. DCB test and fracture toughness measurement

4.1 DCB tests

A non-adhesive PTFE film was inserted into the specimen at the middle plane of the DCB during fabrication process [14]. Two piano hinges were mounted on the surfaces at the specimen's ends. In the test, the piano hinges were clamped by a pair of fixtures of the test machine. The end of the specimen was opened by a constant speed of 1-2mm/min and controlled by displacement mode. Both edges of the specimen ahead of the insert were coated with a thin layer of water-based typewriter correction fluid, to

aid in visual detection of delamination onset. Three groups of DCBs with different thicknesses were tested for measuring the interlaminar fracture toughness. Five specimens are tested for each type. The specimen geometrical configurations are given in table 2.

Figure 5: DCB test set-up

Specimen #	Length, l (mm)	Width, w (mm)	Height, h (mm)	Initial Crack Length, a_0 (mm)
S1*5	151.00	25.27	1.32	59
S2*5	150.88	25.27	2.48	59
S3*5	151.00	25.39	3.66	59

Table 2: Summary of DCB dimensions

4.2 Test Results

The three types of specimens are named by S1, S2, and S3, respectively. Each group consists of four or five pieces of valid experiment data. The load-displacements for these types of specimen are shown in Figs.6.

Figure 6: Load-displacement relations of S1, S2 and S3

As shown in Fig.6, linear load-displacement response is observed before the maximum load, where the crack starts to propagate. Then, the crack propagation went through a relatively stable process. The growing crack length and its associated load and displacement are recorded during the test. The crack length, load and displacement will be used in the calculation of the fracture toughness. It is also noteworthy that there is some variation in the load-displacement curve. These variations are caused by a finite crack growth and introduce the uncertainty in the measuring of the load-displacement associated with that crack length. In addition, the measurement of the growing crack is tedious.

After DCB tests, unidirectional tensile tests were conducted for all of the tested specimens to get their Young's modulus along the fiber direction. The test procedure of measuring the Young's modulus is followed by the ASTM E111-04 [15]. The results are given in Table. 3.

Table 3: Summary of E-moduli

Sample #	Type1 (MPa)	Type2 (MPa)	Type3 (MPa)
1	92095	96675	100650
2	94915	101105	104390
3	98455	97735	100015
4	90640	98500	104275

A series of discrete data including crack length, load and displacement was obtained for each test. Using the MBT, CC, and MCC methods, the interlaminar fracture toughness results for can be obtained. The average values and the variation of the energy release rates from different crack lengths are given in Fig.7 where the center symbol represent the average value, the top and bottom bars are the maximum and minimum energy release rates from these crack lengths. In addition, using the Young's modulus E_{II} from the tensile test and the load-displacement from the test machine, the fracture toughness can also be determined, which are given in Fig.7 as well. It is observed that the average value of the fracture toughness obtained by LD method is consistent with the results from the ASTM recommended methods.

Figure 7: Comparisons of fracture toughness from different methods for S1, S2 and S3

5. Concluding remarks

The DCB specimen is widely used in the measurement of the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite material. There are various kinds of equations for calculating the energy release rate for the DCB by using the elementary beam theory. By using the load-displacement relation at the beam tip, these equations can be easily transferred into the interested one. It is interesting to find that even all these equations are based on the same theory and are mathematically the same. However, the accuracy in the calculating the energy release rate are different. It is found that Eq.(11) is the most accurate in calculating the energy release rate, compared with the alternative equations Eqs.(6-9). The maximum difference of the energy release rates from Eq.(11) and the finite element analysis is about 0.5% even for short composite beam. However, there are remarkable differences between the energy release rates obtained from Eqs.(6-9) and FEM, especially for relatively short composite beam.

Equation (11) is very accurate in calculating the energy release rate. In addition, the crack length a is not included in this equation. Therefore, the shortcoming of measuring a growing crack length in the ASTM methods is overcome. A procedure based on Eq.(11) for measuring the interlaminar fracture toughness is proposed. An additional tensile test for the tested DCB specimen is used to obtain the unidirectional Young's module E_{11} of the composite material for this method. Three different thickness of DCB samples are used to verify the accuracy of the present method. It is found that the interlaminar fracture toughness obtained from this method is consistent with the results obtained by using the ASTM standard methods. However, the present method is easy to conduct, compared with the ASTM procedure.

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